

Level of Awareness and Utilization of Library Services Among Selected 2nd Year Nursing Students at Perpetual Help College of Manila and its Effect on their NCM 107 Lecture Grade

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Abstract

The purpose of this quantitative correlational study is to determine the relationship between the academic performance of selected second-year nursing students at Perpetual Help College of Manila, as measured by their NCM 107 lecture grades, and their awareness of and use of library services. It specifically sought to assess the respondents' level of awareness of the library services, their extent of utilization, and whether there was a substantial correlation between these factors and their academic performance.

Purposive sampling was used to pick 173 respondents for the correlational research design study. A standardized questionnaire based on a Likert scale was used to gather data. To determine a correlation between the variables, the collected data were examined using weighted mean, standard deviation, p-value, frequency, and

percentage distribution, and Spearman Rank Correlation Coefficient (ρ).

Results revealed that the respondents demonstrated a moderate level of awareness and a moderate level of utilization of library services. However, the findings indicated no significant correlation between the level of awareness and utilization of library services and the students' NCM 107 lecture grades. The study concludes that while students are aware of and make use of library resources, these factors alone do not significantly influence their academic performance. It is recommended that future studies explore other variables, such as study habits, learning styles, and motivation, that may have a greater impact on nursing students' academic achievement.

Keywords: *Library Services, Awareness, Utilization, Nursing Students, NCM 107*

INTRODUCTION

Libraries play a vital worldwide role in enhancing academic performance by providing equal access to both digital and physical resources. However, students' awareness of the actual use of library resources, both physical and digital are is determined by how knowledgeable they are of the available services being offered. Understanding the relationship of both can contribute to students effectively; library services can enhance research skills, improve comprehension of academic content, and support independent learning. Nursing students who actively use research databases, digital journals, and other academic resources are more likely to develop critical thinking and analytical skills, both of which are essential in clinical reasoning and academic performance.

The findings of the study may contribute to creating effective strategies such as workshops, orientation programs, and digital literacy training, to improve students' access to and usage of platforms like Philippine E-Journals, EBSCO, and E-Library. Previous studies support the relevance of this study. According to Benue State School of Nursing and Midwifery in Makurdi (2019), despite awareness, students exhibit poor utilization that limits their academic potential. According to a study conducted in 2023 at the Sri Sathya Sai Institute of Higher Learning, Anantapur Campus, 62.67% of students borrowed books on a variety of subjects, including exams, and 32% of students visited frequently. However, many students still demonstrated limited engagement with the available services. Furthermore, according to the National

Library of the Philippines (2023), contemporary libraries provide both digital and physical services, enabling students to access resources at any time and from any location to meet their educational needs. As libraries provide technology-based learning, the proper utilization, and alignment of library services with academic requirements, especially for nursing education, becomes increasingly important.

Research Questions

This study aims to determine the level of utilization of library services among the selected 2nd-year nursing students at Perpetual Help College of Manila and its impact on their NCM 107 lecture grade.

Most specifically, it seeks to answer the following questions:

1. What is the respondents' demographic information in terms of:
 - 1.1 Gender
 - 1.2 Age
 - 1.3 Section
2. What is the respondents' level of awareness of library services in terms of:
 - 2.1 Digital Services (EBSCO and Philippine E-Journals)
 - 2.2 Circulation Services
 - 2.3 Laptop Area
 - 2.4 Borrowing of Bookstand
 - 2.5 Periodical Section
 - 2.6 Discussion Area
 - 2.7 Selective Dissemination of Information
3. What is the respondents' level of utilization of library services in terms of:
 - 3.1 Digital Services (EBSCO and Philippine E-Journals)
 - 3.2 Circulation Services
 - 3.3 Laptop Area
 - 3.4 Borrowing of Bookstand
 - 3.5 Periodical Section
 - 3.6 Discussion Area
 - 3.7 Selective Dissemination of Information
4. What is the grade of the respondents in NCM 107 Lecture for the academic year 2024-2025 (First Semester)?
5. Is there a significant relationship between the respondents' level of utilization of library services to their NCM 107 lecture grades?
6. Based on the findings, what enhancements to library services can be recommended?

Literature Review

A study conducted by MM Yashir Ahamed, Ruth Lalthlamuanpuii, Bhagyashree Chetia, and Dr. Lalngaizuali (2024), titled “Uses of Library Resources and Services by the Nursing Students: A Case Study of College of Nursing, RIMS, Imphal”, explored the utilization of library resources and services among undergraduate nursing students. The findings of the study indicate that the individuals who utilize libraries frequently are the undergraduate nursing students, with a percentage of 86.04%, and have a 50% library visit at least once a week. The findings did determine that the activities in the said library include borrowing books (22%), completing assignments (20.33%), and engaging in self-study (14.14%). The study highlights that the continued usage of undergraduate nursing students with the library’s services and resources has a significant impact on their academic and clinical competency. The study's findings provide empirical evidence of how students' academic and clinical competencies are enhanced by frequent utilization of libraries. These findings form the foundation of the current study, as evaluating the awareness and utilization of library services among second-year nursing students at Perpetual Help College of Manila could identify potential barriers or opportunities in utilizing library services to improve their academic and clinical performance.

Jayaraj and U, K. B. (2021) investigated the awareness and utilization of library resources and services by M. Com students and faculty members in college libraries of Udupi District. The results of the study conducted at the college libraries in the Karnataka State-Udupi District are extremely encouraging in terms of support from libraries for students' academic success. While most of the respondents, both the students (33.8%) and faculty members (33.3%), visit the library daily, this indicates an extremely high level of engagement with the library. This explains that the students and faculty members generally respect the library as a learning resource and regard it as important for their academic endeavors. The students and teachers visit the library to consult books (95.6%), read newspapers and magazines (68.8%), and to take notes/lectures (50.6%). It indicates that the main purpose of visits by students and teachers is formal-that is, to take instructional material, current affairs, and lectures. The students and teachers are mostly aware of the library's textbooks, reference books, journals, dictionaries, and encyclopedias. It means that the library has communicated clearly with its users about its core resources. Most of the respondents are satisfied with circulation services (77.33%), reference services (70.67%), and newspaper clipping services (83.8%). This indicates that students and faculty members are satisfied with the basic services provided by the library. Such findings portray positive engagement by students and faculty with the library, therefore reiterating that it is essential to create an attractive and supportive environment so they can keep coming in.

According to Tofi (2019), student nurses at Benue State Schools of Nursing and Midwifery, Makurdi, must make effective utilization of information resources in order to acquire the skills necessary for research and educating future nurses. These include materials both in the traditional print edition and electronic ones through online journals and databases. However, research points out that most students undergo a lot of struggles as they are not well aware of these resources and further lack of training skills. Some students base their work largely on very few resources such as lecture notes and internet search engines, which might adversely affect their academic performance. On this, some proposed strategies include mass orientation programs, workshops, and seminars with the view of orienting the students better with the resources available, developing their research skills, and making them understand digital tools or resources. Collaboration among nursing faculty and library personnel is also encouraged to include information resources into the curriculum, develop tailored resource guides, and introduce library-related assignments.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This study uses a quantitative, correlational design to explore how nursing students' awareness and use of library services at Perpetual Help College of Manila are linked to their NCM 107 grades. This approach helps the researchers understand the connection between library usage and academic performance. Additionally, a descriptive part was included to look at patterns in how students use the library. It looked at trends, gaps, and ways to improve library services. Data was collected through survey questionnaires, which asked how often students use the library, what resources they are aware of and often utilize, and how these affect their grades in NCM 107. This approach gives a simple view of how libraries use links to academic success and offers ideas for enhancing services. The data were collected using survey questionnaires. These gather information about how often students use the library, what resources they use, and how these resources help their studies. This study uses a quantitative, correlational research design to explore the link between nursing students' awareness and use of library services at Perpetual Help College of Manila and their NCM 107 lecture grades. This design helps understand how library usage and academic performance are connected.

Respondents/Participants

This study emphasizes the familiarity and awareness of the selected 2nd year nursing students with various library services offered at Perpetual Help College of Manila, as well as to determine the frequency and effectiveness of the usage of these resources offered to them to assist in their academic needs and clinical learning. The scope of the study is limited only to 2nd year nursing students studying at Perpetual Help College of Manila, with a subject of NCM 107, which has a total of at least one hundred seventy-three (173) respondents. They were the chosen respondents because they are the subjects of the study and due to their significant engagement in both academic and clinical practice. The researchers believed that the number of respondents was enough to provide ample data and took into account the available population, time constraints, and resources to achieve the specific objectives of this study.

Instruments of the Study

A structured questionnaire was used to collect data for this study on the level of awareness and utilization of library services among Nursing students at Perpetual Help College of Manila and its effect on their NCM 107 Lecture grades. The questionnaire was divided into four sections:

(1) Demographic Profile, which included information on age, gender, section, and frequency of library visits; (2) Level of Awareness of Library Services, which was measured using a 5-point Likert scale that ranged from 1 (Not Aware at All) to 5 (Fully Aware); (3) Level of Utilization of Library Services, which was also measured using a 5-point Likert scale that ranged from 1 (Never) to 5 (More Than 7 Times a Week); and (4) NCM 107 Lecture grade, pass, fail, or incomplete. Higher scores indicated higher awareness or more frequent utilization of library services. Sections 2 and 3 were scored by computing the average responses per item. A Chi-Square test was used to examine correlations between Part 4 data and library service utilization.

Procedure

Prior to data collection, formal permission to conduct the study was obtained by the researchers from the administration of Perpetual Help College of Manila by providing formal letters to the Dean of the College of Nursing and the presidents of each of the seven second-year sections. A three-step validation process was implemented on the structured questionnaire to ensure its accuracy and quality. The structured questionnaire was first validated by a statistician and three academic members from the College of Nursing to ensure that it was reliable, clear, and relevant to the goal of the study. Second, a pilot test was conducted with 30 nursing students. The researchers assessed the students' comprehension of each item and noted any sections that required revisions as they completed the questionnaire under conditions similar to the real data gathering. Lastly, Cronbach's alpha was used to assess the reliability of each component: awareness, utilization, and grades, with values of 0.70 or higher being acceptable.

After validation, nursing students enrolled in NCM 107 from all seven sections were then invited to participate voluntarily. During class hours, the structured questionnaire, created as a Google Form, was disseminated, along with detailed instructions to guarantee truthful and accurate responses. A 5-point Likert scale was used to evaluate responses from Sections 2 and 3 in order to assess respondents' awareness of and utilization of library services. A Chi-Square test was used to examine Part 4, which contains NCM 107 lecture grades, in order to determine the correlation between academic performance and library service utilization. To ensure the reliability and validity of the findings, all data were handled with confidentiality and systematically analyzed.

Data Analysis

The Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) was used to process and evaluate the responses gathered. To summarize the data and identify correlations between variables, descriptive and inferential statistics were used. Frequency counts and percentage distributions were used to examine demographic data, such as age, gender, frequency of library visits, and grades from NCM 107 lectures, to describe the characteristics of the respondents.

A 5-point Likert scale was used to measure respondents' awareness and utilization of library services in Parts 2 and 3 of the survey. Every point on the scale represented a verbal interpretation of the level of awareness (from "Fully Aware" to "Not Aware at All") and the frequency of use (from "More than 7 times a week" to "Never"). The overall awareness and utilization levels were calculated by taking the mean of each item. Depending on the part examined, the responses were categorized using weighted mean ranges into "Fully Aware," "Moderately Aware," or "Somewhat Aware," as well as "More than 7 times a week," "5 to 7 times a week," or "Never."

To evaluate the response variability, the standard deviation was computed as well. Low variability was indicated by values between 0 and 1.0, moderate variability was indicated by values between 1.0 and 1.5, and high variability among respondents' responses was indicated by values above 1.5. This allowed the researchers to determine whether the usage patterns and perceptions of the respondents varied significantly or were consistent.

Inferential statistics were used to determine if the respondents' level of utilization of library services and their NCM 107 lecture grades were significantly correlated. The level of statistical significance was indicated by the p-value derived from the analysis; values less than 0.05 were considered to be significant. Additionally, the direction and strength of the relationship between academic performance and library service use were evaluated using Spearman's Rank Correlation. Perfect correlation was indicated by correlation coefficients (ρ) of 1 or -1 , whereas little or no correlation was indicated by values near 0. In

order to ensure accuracy, validity, and reliability, all statistical processes were carried out using SPSS, and findings were evaluated using standard statistical criteria.

Ethical Considerations

Throughout the study, the researchers ensured that every ethical principle for conducting research was strictly observed. A formal letter requesting consent for conducting the online survey had been distributed to the presidents of all Level II sections and the dean of the College of Nursing prior to data collection. The study was only started after obtaining their approval. The participation of all the respondents was entirely voluntary. Prior to the completion of the Google Form questionnaire, they were informed to told that there would be no consequences if they declined or withdrew at any point.

Anonymity and confidentiality were fully maintained. All the responses were collected without names, and no personally identifiable information was gathered. Only the researchers had access to the safely stored data, which was used solely for academic purposes. The study adhered to the ethical principles of justice, beneficence, and respect for persons. Participation was not intended to result in any psychological, emotional, or physical harm.

RESULTS

Respondents' Demographic Information (Table 1.1, 1.2, and 1.3)

1.1 Gender

Gender	Frequency (n=173)	Percent
Male	29	16.8%
Female	144	83.2%
TOTAL	173	100.0%

Table 1.1 shows the respondents' demographic data for gender. Of the 173 respondents (N=173), there are female participants composed of the vast majority (n=144, 83.2%), while the smaller proportion (n=29, 16.8%) are male participants.

1.2 Age

Age	Frequency (n=173)	Percent
17-18 years old	4	2.3%

19-20 years old	119	68.8%
21 years old and above	50	28.9%
TOTAL:	173	100.0%

The table above shows the age of the respondents. Based on the results, 17-18 years old have 4 or 2.3%, 19-20 years old have 119 or 68.8%, and 21 years old and above have 51 or 28.8%. It also reveals that most of the respondents are 19-20 years old.

1.3 Level of Frequency of Library Visit for Academic Purposes

Frequency of Library Visits for Academic Purposes	Frequency (n=173)	Percent
1 – 2 times a week	117	67.6%
3 – 5 times a week	36	20.8%
More than 5 times a week	7	4.0%
Never	13	7.5%
TOTAL	173	100.0%

The table above shows the Frequency of Library Visits for Academic Purposes. Based on the results, 1 – 2 times a week has 117 or 67.6%, 3 – 5 times a week has 36 or 20.8%, more than 5 times a week has 7 or 4.0%, and never has 13 or 7.5%. The figure also reveals that most of the respondents visited the library 1-2 times a week.

1.4 Level of Awareness of Library Services

How aware are you of the following library services available at the PHCM Library?	Mean	Std. Dev.	Interpretation
Digital Library Services such as EBSCO (an online research database platform) and the Philippine E-Journals (an online collection of academics published in the Philippines)	3.75	1.20	Moderately Aware
Circulation Services (lending and returning physical library materials such as books)	4.12	0.99	Moderately Aware

Laptop Area (an area in the library where the students can use their own laptops)	4.10	1.05	Moderately Aware
Borrowing of Bookstand (physical support or holder designed to display or hold books for easy viewing or access)	3.58	1.27	Moderately Aware
Periodical Section (designated area where students can borrow publications that that are issued regularly such as magazines and newspapers)	3.62	1.19	Moderately Aware
Discussion Area (space where students can engage in group discussions, collaborative work, or study sessions)	3.95	1.11	Moderately Aware
Selective Dissemination of Information (involves providing users with tailored information based on their specific needs or interests)	3.63	1.21	Moderately Aware
Overall Mean	3.82	1.15	Moderately Aware

Table 1.4 shows that respondents got an overall mean awareness total of 3.82 (SD=1.15), which is stated as Moderately Aware. This interprets that nursing students are generally knowledgeable regarding the services offered by the library. When individual library services are analyzed, the highest levels of awareness are Circulation Services (M=4.12, SD=1.27), Laptop Area (M=3.95, SD=1.11), and Discussion Area (M=3.95, SD=1.11). Lowest mean scores interpreted as Moderately Aware are Borrowing of Bookstand (M=3.58, SD=1.27) and Periodical Section (M=3.62, SD=1.19). In summary, all of the library services were identified to have a Moderately Aware interpretation, and the highest awareness on the Circulation Services, Laptop Area, and Discussion Area.

1.5 Level of Utilization of Library Services of the Respondents

How often do you utilize the following library services available at the PHCM Library?	Mean	Std. Dev.	Interpretation
Digital Library Services such as EBSCO (an online research database platform) and Philippine E-Journals (an online collection of academics journals published in the Philippines)	2.80	1.41	2 to 4 times a week

Circulation Services (lending and returning physical library materials such as books)	2.72	1.32	2 to 4 times a week
Laptop Area (an area in the library where the students can use their own laptops)	2.79	1.45	2 to 4 times a week
Borrowing of Bookstand (physical support or holder designed to display or hold books for easy viewing or access)	2.54	1.34	Once a week
Periodical Section (designated area where students can borrow publications that that are issued regularly)	2.57	1.30	Once a week

such as magazines and newspapers)			
Discussion Area (space where students can engage in group discussions, collaborative work, or study sessions)	2.94	1.33	2 to 4 times a week
Selective Dissemination of Information (involves providing users with tailored information based on their specific needs or interests)	2.72	1.28	2 to 4 times a week
Overall Mean	2.72	1.35	2 to 4 times a week

Table 1.5 shows that the most frequently utilized library service was Discussion Area ($M=2.94$, $SD=1.33$), defined as being used 2 to 4 times a week. Following the Discussion Area were Digital Library Services ($M=2.72$, $SD=1.32$), and Laptop Area ($M=2.79$, $SD=1.45$), both of which were also utilized 2 to 4 times a week. The Circulation Services ($M=2.72$, $SD=1.32$) and Selective Dissemination of Information ($M=2.71$, $SD=1.28$) are also within the 2 to 4 times a week. For the lower utilization result, interpreted as once a week, were Periodical Section ($M=2.57$, $SD=1.30$) and Borrowing of Bookstand ($M=2.54$, $SD=1.34$).

1.6 The Grade of the Respondents in NCM 107 Lecture for Academic Year 2024-2025 (First Semester)

NCM 107 Lecture Grade for Academic Year 2024-2025 (First Semester)	Frequency (n=173)	Percent
Passed	169	97.7%
Incomplete	2	1.2%
Failed	2	1.2%
TOTAL	173	100.0%

Table 1.6 shows that out of 173 respondents who are enrolled in the NCM 107 Lecture, there are 169 (97.7%) who passed the subject. While 2 (1.2%) failed and 2 (1.2%) are incomplete.

1.7 The Significant Relationship Between the Respondents' Level of Utilization of Library Services to Their NCM 107 Lecture Grades

Correlation Analysis

Relationship of the following to Lecture Grade	Spearman Rank	p-value	Interpretation	Decision	Remarks
Awareness	0.023	0.759	No Relationship	Do Not Reject Ho	Not Significant
Utilization	-0.026	0.738	No Relationship	Do Not Reject Ho	Not Significant

Reject Ho if $p < 0.05$; significant

Table 1.7 shows that the Spearman's Rank correlation analysis was used to figure out the relationship between respondents' level of utilization of library services and their NCM 107 lecture grades. Significance level was set at 0.05. Correlation coefficient for level of utilization of library services and NCM 107 lecture grades was $R_s = -0.026$, $p\text{-value} = 0.738$. Correlation coefficient for awareness and NCM 107 lecture grades was $R_s = 0.023$, $p\text{-value} = 0.759$. Both of the p-values (0.738 and 0.759) are greater than the significance level of 0.05. Thus, Ho is not rejected. Therefore, there is no significant relationship between the respondents' level of utilization of library services to their NCM 107 lecture grades.

DISCUSSION

This study aimed to determine the level of awareness and utilization of library services among nursing students at Perpetual Help College of Manila and to determine their impact on academic performance in the NCM 107 lecture grade.

The demographic profile of the respondents showed that the majority are female students, comprising 83.5%, while only 16.5% are male students. Most of the students fall within the age range of 19-20 years old (68.8%), followed by those aged 21 and above (29.0%), and a small percentage of the 17-18 age group (2.3%). These results give an insight into the general composition of the nursing student population that was involved in this study.

In terms of the level of awareness of library services, the respondents showed a moderate level of awareness, having an overall mean score of 3.80, with a standard deviation of 1.16. Of all the library services available, the respondents are most aware of circulation services, which include borrowing and returning of books, and the designated laptop area. In contrast, the respondents were less aware with the periodical section and borrowing of books from stands. These findings conclude that while the nursing students recognize the significance of the essential library services, there are still library services that need further promotion to increase the level of awareness of the nursing students.

In the level of utilization of library services, the study determined that the respondents generally use the library services 2 to 4 times a week, with an overall mean score of 2.71 and a standard deviation of 1.35. The discussion area was recognized as the most frequently used library service, stating a preference for group study sessions and collaborative learning. The borrowing of bookstands and utilizing periodical sections were indicated as the least commonly used library services. This concludes that while the nursing students engage with certain aspects of the library services, others remain underutilized.

The study also determined the 2nd year nursing students' grade in NCM 107 Lecture, stating that the majority successfully passed the subject (97.7%), while only a small percentage was incomplete (1.1%) and failed (1.1%). These findings stated a generally high NCM 107 Lecture passing rate among the respondents.

An essential part of the study was determining whether the level of utilization of library services had a significant relationship with the NCM 107 lecture grade. The result showed that there was no significant relationship ($p > 0.05$). The results of this study emphasize the value of understanding how nursing students engage with the library services offered, and how these library services contribute to their academic performance in their NCM 107 lecture grade. Although the nursing students show moderate level of awareness and level of utilization of library services, there is a lack of direct correlation with their NCM 107 lecture grade that includes additional factors that influence their academic performance on NCM 107 lecture grade. This study concluded that while the library services remain a valuable academic resource to the nursing students, the direct impact to their NCM 107 lecture grade seems to be limited. Nevertheless, suggesting that the nursing students are well informed about and encouraged to utilize a larger range of the available library services could possibly give enhancement to their overall academic performance.

Conclusion

This study investigated the awareness and utilization of library services among nursing students at Perpetual Help College of Manila (PHCM) and their correlation with academic performance in NCM 107. The findings reveal a predominantly female student population (83.2%) largely aged 19-20, with

most students utilizing the library one to two times weekly. While awareness of library services was moderate (mean score 3.82), with circulation services and laptop access being the most recognized, utilization patterns indicated a preference for the library as a study space over print materials. The high pass rate in NCM 107 (97.7%) contrasted with the lack of significant correlation between library service awareness/utilization and academic performance ($p = 0.759$ and $p = 0.738$, respectively). This suggests that while the library provides valuable resources, its direct influence on NCM 107 grades is minimal. Other factors, including individual study habits, teaching methodologies, and access to external learning resources, likely play a more significant role in determining academic success. Therefore, while the library remains a crucial academic support, maximizing its impact requires a multi-pronged approach. Institutions should implement strategies to enhance student engagement with underutilized resources through targeted awareness campaigns and faculty integration of library materials into coursework. Further research should explore the influence of factors such as study techniques, time management, and teaching effectiveness on student outcomes to provide a more comprehensive understanding of academic success. Ultimately, proactive and strategic library utilization can significantly enrich the learning experience and contribute positively to student achievement, although its direct impact on grades may be less pronounced than other contributing factors.

REFERENCES

- Ahamed, M. Y., Lalthlamuanpuii, R., Chetia, B., & Dr. Lalngaizuali. (2024). Usage of Library Resources and Services by the Nursing Students: A case study of College of Nursing, RIMS, Imphal 1st ed., Vol. 13.
- Ajibona, H. F., Abomoge, S. O., Adepoju, S. O., & Oluwaniyi, S. A. (2019). Library Services Provision on Academic Performance of Nursing Undergraduates in Selected Universities in South-West Nigeria. *Library Philosophy and Practice*.
- Alligood, M. R. (2021). Florence Nightingale: Modern Nursing. *Nursing Theorists and Their Work* (10th ed., pp. 50-65). Elsevier Health Sciences.
- Alligood, M. R. (2021). Patricia Benner: Caring, Clinical Wisdom, and Ethics in Nursing Practice. *Nursing Theorists and Their Work* (10th ed., pp. 98-119). Elsevier Health Sciences.
- Ata, M., Rani, R., Mostafa, A., & Barua, H. (2020). Library Usage by the Medical Students of a Tertiary Medical College in Chattogram. *Chattogram Maa-O-Shishu Hospital Medical College Journal*. 19. 38-42.
- Jaja C.A. and Udumukwu I.J. (2023) Utilization of School Library and Students' Academic Achievement in Abuja Federal Capita Territory, *International Journal of Library and Information Science Studies*, Vol.9, No.6, pp.61-72.
- Jayaraj, P., and U, K., B. (2021). Awareness and Utilization of Library Resources and Services by M. Com Students and Faculty Members in College Libraries of Udupi District: A Case Study. *Library Philosophy and Practice*.
- Kala, T., & Jayabal, R. (2019). Use and User Perception of Library Collection and Services by the Cherraan's College of Nursing Students, Coimbatore, Tamil Nadu. *Indian Journal of Information Sources and Services*.

- Matta, P. S., & Rao, B. P. (n.d.). Awareness and Utilization of Library resources and services by the students of Sri Sathya Sai Institute of Higher Learning, Anantapur Campus. University of Nebraska - Lincoln.
- Tofi, S. T. (2019). Effective Utilization of Information Resources for Research in Nurses in Benue State Schools of Nursing and Midwifery, Makurdi. ProQuest.
- Tubulingane, B. S. (2021). University Library Services and Student Academic Performance. International Journal of Library and Information Services.